

NOTES

Fluoberyllates of Organic Bases

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Fluoberyllates have long been shown to be isomorphous with sulfates¹. Recently fluoberyllic acid² H_2BeF_4 has been isolated and studied by Ray and his co-workers. The dissociation constants of the fluoberyllic acid $K_1 = 3.462 \times 10^{-3}$ and $K_2 = 1.656 \times 10^{-3}$ show that both the acid and normal salts can be prepared under suitable conditions. In the present communication we report the preparation of some new organic fluoberyllates.

EXPERIMENTAL

All reagents used were of A.R. grade except fluoberyllic acid which was prepared in the laboratory². Beryllium, Fluorine and Nitrogen were estimated by usual procedures.

General methods of preparation: All the normal fluoberyllates were prepared by (a) metathesis reaction between the amine hydrochlorides and thallos fluoberyllate, (b) neutralisation of fluoberyllic acid by various amines.

Details of (a): The amine hydrochloride in aqueous solution was slowly added to an aqueous solution of thallos fluoberyllate drop by drop at low temperature (0°). The precipitated thallos chloride was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 at 0°. The crystals obtained were dried between folds of filter papers, and then in air and analysed.

Details of (b): Fluoberyllic acid in a polythene beaker was neutralised by the amine slowly, drop by drop, with constant stirring, at 0° till the precipitation of beryllium hydroxide starts. The beaker was kept aside for an hour at 0°. Then the precipitated beryllium hydroxide was filtered off and the filtrate was crystallised in a vacuum desiccator over conc. H_2SO_4 at 0°. The crystals obtained were filtered, dried between folds of filter papers, then in air and analysed.

The analytical results and the properties of the different fluoberyllates prepared are tabulated in Table 1.

TABLE I

Compounds	Methods of preparation	Analytical results	General properties
(1) Pyridine fluoberyllate (C ₅ H ₅ NH) ₂ BeF ₄	(1) Method (a)	(1) Found : Be = 3.42% F = 31.53% Calculated : Be = 3.67% F = 31.02%	(1) Readily soluble in water, solution neutral to litmus. On keeping the solution for a long time beryllium hydroxide was found to be precipitated. On heating the crystals to 200° basic vapours were found to be evolved.
(2) Quinoline fluoberyllate (C ₈ H ₇ NH) ₂ BeF ₄	(2) Method (a)	(2) Found : Be = 2.76% F = 22.44% Calculated : Be = 2.61% F = 22.03%	(2) Same as (1)
(3) Triethylamine fluoberyllate [(C ₂ H ₅) ₃ NH] ₂ BeF ₄	(3) Method (a) and (b) both	(3) Found : Be = 3.31% F = 25.88% Calculated : Be = 3.11% F = 26.29%	(3) Same as (1)
(4) Ethylene diamine fluoberyllate (C ₂ N ₂ H ₈) ₂ BeF ₄	(4) Method (a) and (b) both.	(4) Found : Be = 4.18% F = 36.36% N = 27.12% Calculated : Be = 4.35% F = 36.7% N = 27.3%	(4) Solution alkaline to litmus. Other properties same as in (1).
(5) Aniline fluoberyllate (C ₆ H ₅ NH ₂) ₂ BeF ₄	(5) Method (a) and (b) both	(5) Found : Be = 3.46% F = 28.22% Calculated : Be = 3.29% F = 27.83%	(5) Same as (1)
(6) Triethanolamine fluoberyllate (C ₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ NH) ₂ BeF ₄	(6) Method (a) and (b). Besides, the comp. can be prepared by digesting (NH ₄) ₂ BeF ₄ with tri-ethanolamine.	(6) Found : Be = 2.28% F = 19.62% N = 9.56% Calculated : Be = 2.35% F = 19.8% N = 9.77%	(6) Solution alkaline to litmus. Other properties same as in (1).

REFERENCES

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2. T. Ghosh, T. N. Chakraborty and N. Ray, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 847.